

INTERPRETATION OF THE CHRONOTOPE OF A TRAGIC SITUATION
IN A NON-REALISTIC STORY

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Annotation

This article is about the interpretation of chronology and spirituality by talented writers. The writer, who has deeply analyzed the human spiritual world, assigns a special meaning to the image of the night. The writer sees night as a metamorphosis, the boundary between existence and non-existence. It instills its original ideas into existence in a symbolic form.

Key words: xenophobia, society, conflictology, psychology, antic, method.

Schools are characterized by different types of conflicts.

In fact, art is the product of the writer's thinking, creative concept, pains and sufferings that permeate his entire existence. When the writer writes all joy and sadness from his heart, he pours all the pain and suffering of his existence to the listener. He wants a friend who understands him. U. Hamdam is one of the writers who wrote a non-realistic story in the new era in which he freed his heart (metamorphosis) and showed the transformation that literature should be like this. In the people of the East, a person has a secret that he cannot tell anyone. And U. Hamdam approaches the issue in a different way: he never hides his sincerity in front of the reader. He perfectly perceives both death and life, the disappointments that caused it, and the participants in the process. If we say "Loneliness" is one of such stories, we will not be mistaken: "My son died in agony... Before his death, the doctors pulled out the instruments that were stuck in his body and said, "He will come out now. then you will take it away," he said. They behaved as if they were handing over a healthy child to us. I said to beat them all together, and after seeing from God, I suppressed myself. And the boy did not hesitate when he said

yes. We waited for a long time, about two hours. For some reason, he went and told many people, "Muhammad, my son's name is Muhammad!" I said one by one"¹.

The writer tells about his life between the village and the city (Andijan and Tashkent), which turns into a mirage in the art of short stories, and the most terrible situation of the hero, his psyche becomes more real with the death of his son. He considers himself guilty of his son's death. He would have saved his son from death if he had not filled the gaps in his family in order to show people the true colors of the world. Fate puts such a stamp on his forehead. He will live in agony for the rest of his life. As a result, other events in the story are revealed openly after this funeral ceremony. So, the metamorphosis of the writer - not realizing that he is between the city and the village, sometimes lamenting to God, committing all kinds of sins in front of him, and later begging for consolation and repentance is one of them. Death is right! It also follows lust. Are there few people who sacrifice themselves for the sake of wealth, fame and career, and spend their lives sacrificing others for the sake of lust? The writer suffers for a lifetime between these two grasses. In fact, this is one of the main reasons for his loneliness.

In the story above, the tragic situation takes place in the chronotope village, in the house where he was born and raised. In the plot and composition of the work, the tragic situation destroys the existence of the hero. He left for the city in search of knowledge, hoping to become a writer, scientist, and a philosopher-historian, but his marriage in the chaos of his unexpected highness brought him to face terrible trials. The tragic mood now begins to live in his psyche, in his being:

“Everyone was crying, I even saw tears in the eyes of strangers. Only his father - my eyes were dry. I tried - it didn't work. Then I was wandering. In the

¹ Ҳамдамов Улуғбек. Узоқдаги Дилнура. Қисса ва ҳикоялар. –Т.: “Академнашр”. 2010. –Б.28.

evening, people dispersed, and only our family members remained in the yard. While I was staring at the flowing water sparkling in the moonlight, suddenly my lungs were full, and pain shot out from my stomach. I couldn't stop myself and began to cry.”²

What was the reason for the father's alienation and withdrawal from people in this scene? Why didn't everyone shed a single tear at his son's funeral? Did he give so much stone? No, he thinks that there is no use of dry tears during his life of tears, and the important thing is that a person should feel remorse for his actions and draw conclusions from his mistakes. This fantasy teaches him to take a deeper look at life, not to be stone-faced. We can see that this sentence is the epitome of all the sufferings of the hero of the play. The real truth of the story is evident in this one sentence. The reader will discover other meanings from it. In such a period, in the transitional period of independence, all the sufferings, sorrows and sorrows of the literary man were scattered in different cells (components) of the story. Random interpretation gives the writer a great opportunity. That is, there is no systematic plot in the story. One event does not give birth to another event. Irregular images in the work only show the important lines of the unrealistic story!

Temurpolat Tillayev is the pride of Kashkadarya literary environment and Uzbek literature. He is one of the writers who gained his voice and reputation in the 90s. He creates his own individual style, inspired by writers who brought innovation to the literary literature with their formal and stylistic research, such as Kafka, Camus, and Joyce. In all three stories, the chronotope of the tragic situation is interpreted in its own way. Speaking about this, Prof. B. Yoldoshev noted: “Temirpolat continues his creative research. His new short story "Choh" is stylistically very different from "Voris". In "Choh" Temurpolat's emotions are now expressed in a completely new way. In this story, as we have already said, there is

² Кўрсатилган адабиёт. –Б.28.

conditionality, there are philosophical observations about life. The people of Elsaroy, who are prone to a lot of fun and frivolity, will come out from the brink of disaster one day. This catastrophe begins with the unceasing rain of unearthly red rain upon the Elsaraites”.³ In fact, the tragic situation in the story's architecture, that is, the chronotope related to death, emphasizes the multi-layered and complex nature of the plot. This principle leads a person to catharsis, purification. During the former Soviet Union of the 20th century, people experienced great hardships: two world wars. These events are narrated in a symbolic and metaphorical way. Due to the fact that the story was written at the same time, the unrealism in it was a phenomenon and quickly won the hearts of readers. In the following image, the writer interprets as follows: "My body froze from fear when I picked up the cloak on the dead body. I have seen many dead people because of my profession. It was as if Turon had escaped from the tower of a hundred-story house, he was completely crushed by the impact, his body and limbs were broken and twisted, and there was no way to separate them from each other”⁴. The most characteristic and sad situation in the story, the situation of the tragic chronotope causes a lot of pain in the reader. There is a great philosophy in the death of Turon, the hero of the short story. The event, which aims to show the face of ASL, a society that is spiritually crippled, whose passions have faded, and is prone to tragedies, reminds us of the former union era. Discontinuous changes occur in the nature of the characters moving in the symbolic space. One of the great losses of the 20th century is the ecology of the soul. A person feels lonely in a mentally handicapped and disabled society. The reason we say this is that Stalin's period of repression took away thousands of intellectuals from this world early. In the works of the 20th-century existentialist movement, they put forward the idea that society should

³ Йўлдошев Б. Қашқадарё адиблари. –Т: “Олтин нашр”. 2020 . –Б. 294.

⁴ Тиллаев Т. Ўлим ўққони. –Т.: “Академншр”. 2021. –Б.88-89.

help every person as much as possible to live happily, and brought the war going on inside, in the heart of a person, to the level of art in the language of symbols.

By the 90s, T.Tillayev's short story "Kiss of Death" is a logical answer to this question. There are three images of death in the story. The kiss of death is a symbolic place. It mentally cripples and injures a person, and destroys people's feelings, beliefs and thoughts. This former union combines the hateful policy of the cotton monopoly with a symbolic interpretation. Every detail in the work appears as a carrier of one symbol.

Adabiyotlar

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